

Out of sight, out of mind? Cost of minimizing visibility of nationwide renewable energy systems

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1 Out of sight, out of mind? Cost of minimizing
2 visibility of nationwide renewable energy systems

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23 **Abstract**

24 Visual landscape impacts on scenic and populated places are important factors
25 affecting local acceptance to large-scale renewable energy deployment. Through
26 the combination of large-scale viewshed and techno-economic energy system anal-
27 yses, we assess their potential impacts for nationwide renewable energy systems.
28 In a case study of Germany, moderate consideration of visual impact by siting
29 renewables out of sight of the most scenic and densely populated areas does not
30 have a significant impact on system costs and design. However, with a higher sen-
31 sitivity toward visual impacts, annual system costs would increase by up to 38%

32 in the energy sector in 2045. In addition, this strategy would reduce the resilience
33 of the energy system by increasing the reliance on green hydrogen imports and
34 uncertain mass adoption of rooftop photovoltaics. The visual impact of renewable
35 energies cannot be completely eliminated, but careful planning could lead to a
36 socially-acceptable deployment while understanding the implications for system
37 costs and transformation pathways.

38 A key component in mitigating the intensification of climate change-related extreme
39 events [1–3] is the substitution of conventional fossil fuels with sustainable, low-carbon,
40 renewable energy. Despite their economic competitiveness due to strongly decreasing
41 costs of on- and offshore wind [4–6] as well as solar energy [7, 8], the current growth
42 dynamics of renewable energies are not sufficient to enable 1.5 °C-compatible scenarios
43 [9]. In Europe, and especially Germany, after years of record capacity expansion, the
44 growth rates have recently been declining sharply due to social opposition towards
45 these technologies, especially wind power [5, 10, 11].

46 The construction of on- and offshore wind is increasingly opposed by local stake-
47 holders [12, 13] with the visual impact of the turbines on the landscape being the
48 main concern [14–21]. In particular, turbine installations are rejected in landscapes
49 with high aesthetic quality, while they are more accepted in less beautiful landscapes
50 [22–27]. While solar energy generally has less impact on the landscape [28] and causes
51 less public opposition [29, 30], the visual impact especially of large-scale photovoltaic
52 (PV) systems is seen critically [31] and in specific regions the opposition is stronger
53 than towards wind [32]. Together with other externalities like noise, threats to wildlife
54 and decline of property prices, the visual impacts of renewable technologies appear to
55 diminish for local residents with increasing distance from the plant [26, 33–35].

56 The primary planning approach to mitigate and assess visual landscape impacts
57 from renewable energy projects is visibility analysis [36, 37]. Visibility analysis can be
58 conducted in a variety of ways, including visibility maps generated from viewshed anal-
59 ysis, 3D simulations, and photomontages [38, 39]. However, when planning projects
60 at large spatial scales (i.e., regional or national), the aforementioned methods cannot
61 be efficiently utilized. The reason for this is in the case of viewshed calculation, the
62 analysis is based on a line-of-sight test [40] that is carried out from the perspective of
63 an examined project. Consequently, the exact locations of all examined projects must
64 have been determined first, which is not possible while the locations of those project
65 is still under investigation. Therefore, the use of visibility analysis for planning so far
66 is limited to small spatial scales [41–45] or impact assessments [46, 47]. However, the
67 shortcomings of conventional viewshed analysis can be overcome by reversing their
68 setup, i.e., performing the analyses from the perspective of the landscape areas that
69 are to be protected rather than from the perspective of the examined projects. This
70 reverse viewshed assessment can be expanded to the large-scale planning of renewable
71 energy deployment [48] and will be utilized in the present study.

72 Given the former limitations of visibility analyses, only a few studies [23, 49–51]
73 have attempted to incorporate visual landscape impact considerations into nationwide

74 energy system analyses or transformation studies. In addition, these studies have con-
75 sidered visual landscape impacts in simplified ways or have focused primarily on visual
76 impacts from onshore wind systems [51]. For instance, one study [49] substituted wind
77 turbines entirely with PV systems, which presumably have lower visual impacts, and
78 others [23, 50] excluded onshore wind placements at scenic areas.

79 In this study, we combine mathematical, techno-economic, and landscape planning
80 approaches to answer the following research questions: would it be possible to install
81 a national renewable energy system that would not be visible from scenic or densely
82 populated areas and would face significantly less local opposition?? If so, what would
83 be the costs associated with such an energy system design? We attempt to answer
84 these questions for a case study of Germany by first determining the reverse view-
85 sheds for all populated and scenic places in Germany from individual persons to wind
86 turbines with 130 meters hub-height and photovoltaic plants with 2 meters height.
87 Next, we determine the techno-economic potential in Germany for on- and offshore
88 wind and open-field PV that is not within the viewsheds. Finally, we compare energy
89 system transformation costs by 2045 with and without renewable energy technologies
90 excluded by viewsheds with a national energy system optimization model. To the best
91 of the authors' knowledge, this is the first large-scale analysis that integrates reverse
92 viewsheds of renewable energy systems into feasible renewable potential analyses and
93 techno-economic system transformation planning.

94 **Reverse viewshed maps and scenarios**

95 The reverse viewshed analyses were conducted from every centroid of a 1-kilometer-
96 square grid of Germany to determine theoretically visible areas from different
97 scenicness and population density levels (Fig. 1a). These reverse viewshed maps were
98 then incorporated as exclusion zones in land eligibility assessments (see example in
99 Fig. 1b) along with other geographical, technical, and legal restrictions (see Supple-
100 mentary Table 1). Nine visibility scenarios were then considered to account for people's
101 sensitivity to the visual impact of renewable energy technologies [39] on different land-
102 scapes and to consider the magnitude of the affected population (see sceneario table
103 in Fig. 1b).

104 The logic behind the selected scenarios is as follows: first, we determined the areas
105 available for the placement of renewable energy systems that would not be visible from
106 the most scenic places in Germany, i.e., scenicness level = 9 at a scale of 1 (low scenic-
107 ness) to 9 (high) [52]. Subsequently, the thresholds were gradually increased to also
108 exclude renewable energy systems that are visible from lower scenicness levels down
109 to the average scenicness level in Germany (i.e., excluding renewable energy plants
110 visible from scenicness levels ≥ 8 , ≥ 7 , ≥ 6 , and ≥ 5). The last scenario represents our
111 strictest exclusion criteria that reflect high sensitivity of the population to the visual
112 landscape impacts from renewable infrastructure, even when viewed from the average
113 landscape scenicness. We did not consider lower scenicness levels, as these are mostly in
114 urban areas [11, 52], which we incorporated by similarly considering population density
115 levels. For the latter, we started by determining the available areas that are not visible
116 from high-density urban centers (i.e., population density ≥ 5000 people/km²). Lastly,
117 the thresholds were gradually increased to account for scenarios where renewable

Fig. 1 Methods to calculate reverse-viewshed maps and their use as exclusion zones in the land eligibility assessments. a, Reverse viewshed calculations is utilized to generate area in which the planned wind turbines or open-field PV are potentially visible from people standing at the selected viewpoint (see Methods for more details). The viewpoints used are the centroid of 1-kilometer-square grid of Germany with scenicness level and population density number. The visibility thresholds distance of 11 km was used for wind turbines and 7.5 km for open-field PV. b, Example of integrating reverse viewshed maps from viewpoints with scenicness level = 9 (in purple), and reverse viewshed maps from viewpoints with population density ≥ 5000 people/km² (in brown) into the land eligibility assessment of onshore wind turbines in Aachen, Germany. Green areas represent the available areas for siting of onshore wind turbines based on legal and technical restrictions. Some potential sites located on the border with neighboring municipalities have been cropped, resulting in some green areas shown without turbines. The table on the bottom right shows the nine visibility scenarios considered. For example, the scenario scenicness ≥ 7 excludes all potential turbines or PV modules, that would theoretically be visible from areas with a scenicness level of at least 7.

118 energy systems are not visible even from areas with lower population densities (i.e.,
 119 population density ≥ 3500 people/km², ≥ 1500 people/km², ≥ 300 people/km²).

Renewable energy plants invisible from scenic and densely populated areas

The existing renewable energy plants [53] in Germany are predominantly visible from locations with low scenicness values and low population density (see Supplementary Fig. 3–4). A total of 65% of onshore wind turbines and 86% of the open-field PV projects are visible from locations with scenicness levels of six or lower. As scenicness levels increase, the number of visible plants decreases until only 3% of the total onshore wind turbines and 2% of open-field PV projects are visible from the most scenic locations (i.e., scenicness level = 9). With regard to population density, this trend is less pronounced for onshore wind, but remains consistent for open-field PV: the majority of existing open-field PV projects (77%) are visible from areas with population density below 1500 people/km². Only 2% are visible from densely populated areas with population density above 5000 people/km². For onshore wind, only 18% of the total onshore wind turbines are visible from areas with population density below 1500 people/km², while 12 % are visible from densely populated areas.

Including the existing plants, Germany has a technical capacity potential of 398 GW for onshore wind, 79 GW for offshore wind, and 669 GW for open-field PV (without visibility restrictions). The capacity potentials of onshore wind and open-field PV are gradually reduced as the visibility restriction based on scenicness becomes more restrictive, as shown in Fig. 2. At a scenicness level of 9, the reverse viewsheds exclude renewables that are visible from the most scenic landscapes in Germany, such as the Black Forest and the Bavarian Alps. This results in a reduction of the capacity potential by 10% for onshore wind and 4% for open-field PV. These areas, despite their outstanding scenic quality, are inhabited by less than 0.5% of the German population. However, they might be of significant importance as tourist attractions.

Fig. 2 shows that the capacity potential starts to decrease significantly as plants visible from scenicness level ≥ 7 or lower are excluded. This trend continues and leaves only 3 GW of onshore wind and 44 GW of open-field PV potential in the scenicness ≥ 5 scenario. Designing a renewable energy system that is not visible from areas with the average level of scenicness in Germany would reduce 99.3% of onshore wind and 93.5% of open-field PV capacity potential. In contrast, the capacity potentials and eligible areas for offshore wind remain constant across different visibility scenarios due to legal restrictions that require offshore wind turbines to be placed at least 15 km away from the coast [54]. This distance is greater than the assumed visibility threshold of 11 km (see Methods), below which distance a wind turbine has a significant visual impact on the landscape [55]. Furthermore, Fig. 2 also illustrates that less than 25% of Germany’s population resides in areas with above or average scenicness level. In addition to tourists who visit scenic areas, 20 million residents in these areas could be safeguarded visually from large-scale renewable infrastructure under the strictest scenario considered based on scenicness.

Accounting for visibility from high-density urban centers, such as Berlin and other metropolitan areas, would reduce onshore wind potential by 10% and open-field PV potential by 6% . As illustrated in Fig. 2, as the restrictions on visibility based on population density progress, the areas available for renewable deployment continue to decrease. Ultimately, this leaves only 1.5 GW of onshore wind (99.6% reduction)

Fig. 2 Viewsheds for different scenicness and population density thresholds as exclusion zones and impact on renewable energy potential. Potentials are calculated after considering legal, geographical, and technical constraints. The secondary y-axis in the lower line plots shows the percentage of the population residing in the areas for which the RE (renewable energy) installations are not visible.

165 and 68 GW of solar PV (89.8% reduction) potential that is invisible from areas with
 166 a population density greater than 300 people/km². At this strict scenario, 87% of
 167 Germany population (equivalent to 70 million people) would be protected visually
 168 from large-scale renewable energy infrastructure, viewed from their home. In addition,

169 across all scenarios, the results demonstrate the smaller visual impact of open-field
170 PV systems on the landscape compared to wind turbines.

171 Furthermore, we conducted a simulation to determine the electricity generation
172 potential and the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) at each site for every visibility
173 scenario (Fig. 3). In the base scenario, 398 GW potential of onshore wind turbines
174 could generate 877 $TWh_{el}/year$, whereas 669 GW open-field PV systems could supply
175 728 $TWh_{el}/year$. The graphs again demonstrate that more stringent visibility restric-
176 tions result in a reduction of the potential for both onshore wind and open-field PV.
177 It is worth noting from Fig. 3a. that gradually excluding wind turbines visible from
178 the most scenic areas in Germany also progressively eliminates turbines with high
179 LCOEs. This indicates that some sites with high visual landscape impacts in Ger-
180 many coincide with the worst wind conditions, suggesting an alignment of landscape
181 protection with the objective of cost-effectiveness. This is not the case for visibility
182 restrictions based on population density. Furthermore, the LCOEs for onshore wind
183 power vary considerably across locations in Germany, ranging from €36.1/MWh to
184 €471.1/MWh, with an average of €70.5/MWh in the base scenario. In contrast, the
185 LCOEs of open-field PV systems exhibit less variation, ranging from €57.9/MWh to
186 €78.5/MWh. This suggests that the quality of solar resources is relatively consistent
187 throughout Germany.

188 The German renewable electricity generation targets for 2030 and 2040 [56] are
189 not achievable under the two strictest scenarios based on scenicness (i.e., scenic-
190 ness ≥ 5 , ≥ 6) and population density (i.e., population density ≥ 300 people/km²,
191 ≥ 1500 people/km²). For open-field PV, this is only true for the strictest visibility
192 scenarios considered (i.e., scenicness ≥ 5 and population density ≥ 300 people/km²).

193 **Impacts on system costs and energy transformation pathways**

194 Utilizing the remaining renewable energy potential under different visibility scenarios,
195 we identified cost-optimal transformation pathways for the sector-wide German energy
196 system to achieve the greenhouse gas-neutral goal by 2045. We found that excluding
197 large-scale renewable infrastructure that are visible from the most scenic (scenicness =
198 9) or densely populated areas (population density ≥ 3500 people/km²) does not affect
199 the cost of the optimal system (see Supplementary Fig. 6). The overall system costs
200 start to gradually increase at scenarios excluding renewable energy systems visible
201 from scenicness levels ≥ 8 or population density ≥ 1500 people/km² onwards. Even-
202 tually, restricting renewable energy infrastructures to areas that are not visible from
203 average scenicness onwards (i.e., scenicness levels ≥ 5) results in an increase in the
204 overall system costs by up to €45.5 billion/year in 2045. Furthermore, not employ-
205 ing renewable infrastructures that are visible from areas with an average population
206 density onwards (population density ≥ 300 people/km²) increases system costs by up
207 to €56.4 billion/year in 2045. The majority of these additional costs come from the
208 energy sector, which would experience up to 38% of the cost increases per year in
209 2045 (equivalent to €23.6 billion/year) under these strictest visibility scenarios. The
210 energy sector encompasses electricity generation, imports, and exports.

211 The deployment of alternative technologies, including rooftop PV with lower cost
212 efficiency, is required in response to high visual sensitivity to large-scale renewable

Fig. 3 Cost-potential graphs of onshore wind (a) and open-field PV (b) not visible from different scenianness and population density thresholds. The area in light grey represent the current yearly electricity generation by the end of 2023. The areas in light green and green represent the electricity generation targets for each technology by 2030 and 2040, respectively.

213 energy plants (see Fig. 4b). The massive deployment of rooftop PV necessitates huge
 214 storage development, reflected in the increases in storage sector costs by up to threefold
 215 at scenianness levels ≥ 5 and population density ≥ 300 people/km², compared to the
 216 base scenario. In these strict scenarios, marginal reductions in the infrastructure sector
 217 costs can also be observed (Fig. 4a), as the distributed use of rooftop PV reduces the
 218 necessity for grid expansions.

219 In the base scenario, offshore wind and rooftop PV collectively contribute to only
 220 12.6% of the electricity supply in 2045 (Supplementary Fig. 7). As the visibility restric-
 221 tions progress, the supply from open-field PV and onshore wind is gradually replaced
 222 by rooftop PV and offshore wind power. At the strictest scenarios, rooftop PV and
 223 offshore wind power account for 73% of electricity supply in 2045. This strategy
 224 exhausts the capacity potential for rooftop PV [54] and offshore wind in Germany.
 225 In the industrial and residential sectors (Supplementary Fig. 14 and 15), there are
 226 also notable increases in the natural gas usage at the strictest visibility scenario.
 227 These strategies also necessitate a sudden phase-out of fossil-based fuel in the sectors
 228 within only five years from 2040 to 2045. Furthermore, the non-utilization of onshore
 229 wind and open-field PV due to concerns regarding their visual impact also affects
 230 the green hydrogen supply routes. As illustrated in Fig. 4b, in scenianness ≥ 5 and

Fig. 4 Relative costs deviation by sectors (a) and relative deviation of electricity supply by sources (b) from base scenario, if large-scale renewable energy plants visible from sceniness levels ≥ 5 and population density ≥ 300 people/km² are not utilized. **a.** The cost deviation is shown for each sector. As all sectors are taken into account, these costs include many parts such as the building stock or transport options, which are not as strongly affected by the various scenarios as the energy sector. At the strictest visibility restriction, the cost from energy sector increases by 38% in 2045 (equivalent to €23.6 billion). **b.** Reduction in electricity supplies from onshore wind and open-field PV are substituted by rooftop PV and offshore wind. Blue line shows the need to increase hydrogen imports shares in fulfilling demand at the strictest visibility restrictions.

231 population density ≥ 300 people/km² scenarios, in 2030, 91 – 95% of green hydrogen
 232 supply is imported. This equates to 77 TWh/year of green hydrogen imports in 2030.
 233 In these strict visibility scenarios, the import of hydrogen will remain the predomi-
 234 nant supply route, reaching 300 TWh/year by 2045 (see Supplementary Fig. 10). In
 235 contrast, in the base scenario, domestic production of green hydrogen is the primary
 236 source of hydrogen supply across the modeled years, with the exception of 2045, where
 237 the cost-optimal hydrogen import of 260 TWh/year is required.

238 Discussion

239 We developed a framework that enables *a priori* integration of visual impact consid-
 240 erations into techno-economic energy system planning at a large spatial scale for the
 241 first time. The findings suggest that preventing opposition towards large-scale renew-
 242 able energy by placing those technologies out of sight from scenic and populated areas
 243 might be very costly at high sensitivity scenarios and might reduce the resilience of the

Fig. 5 Annual system costs in 2045 for different visibility scenarios. As all sectors are taken into account, these costs include many parts, such as for the building stock or transport options, which are not as strongly affected by the various scenarios as the energy sector.

244 German energy system (see Fig. 5). Excluding only sites for renewable plants that are
 245 visible from the most densely populated or scenic areas would not lead to a notable
 246 change in the energy system transformation costs (i.e., not visible from scenicness level
 247 = 9 or population density ≥ 3500 people/km²). This indicates that moderately consider-
 248 ing visual impacts is not financially binding. In these scenarios, there is also a slight
 249 preference for open-field PV with lower visual impacts over onshore wind power. With
 250 higher visual sensitivity, the overall system costs increase and a significant adoption
 251 of offshore wind and rooftop PV is required to substitute open-field PV and onshore
 252 wind power. For rooftop PV, up to 18 times of the current rooftop capacity (618 GW)
 253 would be needed by 2045 in the strictest visibility scenarios. This would necessitate an
 254 expansion rate of 29 GW/year until 2045, exhausting the available rooftop potential
 255 [54]. It is questionable whether the current expansion rate for rooftop and open-field
 256 PV in Germany of only 7.5 GW/year could be increased so much. Furthermore, to
 257 assume that all building owners would adopt rooftop PV is highly optimistic, as the
 258 current rooftop PV adoption still faces various challenges due to high upfront invest-
 259 ment [57, 58], unclear ownership and benefit-sharing schemes among landlord and
 260 tenant [59], and low dissemination of information about the technology [57, 58]. For
 261 example, Switzerland has applied a strategy to restrict open-field PV due to landscape
 262 visual impacts and prioritize rooftop PV [60], which is not cost-effective nor spatially
 263 efficient [60]. Placing renewables out of sight from average scenicness and population
 264 density levels would also necessitate a significant proportion of green hydrogen imports
 265 from as early as 2025. This would require the exporting countries to utilize the exist-
 266 ing renewables to produce green hydrogen, which would result in the substitution of
 267 energy supply from renewables with other sources and would risk additional emissions
 268 generation in those exporting countries [61].

269 Our findings align with those of previous studies that suggest the implementa-
 270 tion of moderate exclusion zones to account for the disamenities caused by renewable

271 energy infrastructures [62, 63]. We added to the analysis by providing exclusion zones
272 based on visibility from scenic and populated areas at different sensitivity levels.
273 Our findings indicate that moderate consideration of visual impacts does not affect
274 energy potential, the optimized costs, and energy system transformation. However,
275 more stringent restrictions would result in significant output effects [63] through the
276 utilization of more sites by other, more costly technologies. In addition, this strategy
277 would also require renewable infrastructures to be concentrated offshore or in certain
278 remote areas, as shown in Fig. 2. This may concentrate environmental burdens in
279 the locations not visible from scenic or populated areas and further give rise to con-
280 cerns about distributive justice, given the potential for spatially unequal benefits and
281 burdens associated with such strategies [64, 65]. While the hidden placement of renew-
282 able energies may be a strategy from the spatial planner’s perspective, this approach
283 should not preclude public participation in the decision-making process. Furthermore,
284 visibility from scenic and densely populated areas may encompass partial visibility of
285 infrastructure [39], but not all aspects of the visual impact concerns associated with
286 renewable energy technologies [48]. The concept of visual impacts also encompasses
287 individual perceptions of annoyance, influenced by place attachment. This may be
288 more particularly pronounced in rural and possibly non-scenic areas, which are not
289 considered in this study. Furthermore, site-specific visual impacts, such as shadow
290 flicker phenomena from wind turbines [66], glare from PV [67], or different severity
291 of visual impacts due to cumulative number of concentrated renewable energy plants
292 [68] could be incorporated in future analyses.

293 The framework and findings of this study should serve as tools to facilitate a two-
294 way dialogue between national planners, local stakeholders, and the public with the
295 goal of jointly planning the acceptable deployment of renewables [69, 70] while under-
296 standing the implications of different planning arrangements on the overall energy
297 transformation and system costs.

298 **Methods**

299 **General approach**

300 Our methodology is divided into four steps (see Fig. 6). First, reverse viewshed maps
301 for every kilometer-square of Germany were generated. These viewshed maps have
302 underlying metadata, in our case population numbers and landscape scenicness ratings
303 from 1 (low scenicness) to 9 (high). Second, the influence of viewsheds on renew-
304 able energy potentials of onshore and offshore wind power and open-field solar PV
305 were evaluated. This was done by excluding renewable energy plants visible from dif-
306 ferent population and scenicness thresholds based on the corresponding viewsheds.
307 Using ETHOS.GLAES [54, 71, 72], the reverse-viewshed maps were combined with
308 other regulatory and technical land eligibility constraints for siting utility-scale wind
309 turbine and solar PV in Germany (see Supplementary Table 1). Third, we used
310 ERA5 data to simulate electricity generation for different visibility scenarios within
311 the ETHOS.RESKit framework [72]. Finally, the renewable energy potential scenarios
312 were used to determine the impact of the visibility restrictions on the cost-optimal,
313 greenhouse gas-neutral energy system transformation in Germany by 2045. The energy

314 system optimization was conducted using the model ETHOS.NESTOR, which is based
 315 on the ETHOS.Fine modeling framework [73, 74].

Fig. 6 Overview of the models and data used in this study.

316 Reverse viewshed analysis

317 Reverse viewshed analysis is a viewshed analysis conducted from the perspective of
 318 the landscapes elements that are to be protected, rather than from the perspective of
 319 the proposed renewable energy projects. This analysis enables *a priori* visual impact
 320 assessment of renewable energy infrastructure [48]. It uses user-defined important
 321 landscapes (i.e., scenic areas, densely-populated areas, or protected landscapes) as
 322 viewpoints and generates a Reverse-Zone of Theoretical Visibility (R-ZTV) map that
 323 illustrates the areas in which any future construction of renewable energy infrastruc-
 324 ture, would be visible from important landscapes. The generated R-ZTV map can be
 325 used as an exclusion zone in renewable energy planning to minimize the visual impact
 326 of renewable energy infrastructure on important landscapes. Fig. 1a in the main article
 327 illustrates the principle of reverse viewshed analysis used in this study.

328 We performed the calculation of R-ZTV using the r.viewshed function in GRASS-
 329 GIS [75]. The inputs required for this analysis are a Digital Elevation Model (DEM),
 330 viewpoints generated from the centroids of a 1 km² grid with landscape sceniness rat-
 331 ings (1–9) and population data in Germany, renewable energy infrastructure heights,
 332 observer height, and visibility thresholds. For DEM data, the Digital Surface Model
 333 (DSM) raster file for Germany from Copernicus EU-DEM v1.1 [76] was used. The
 334 sceniness ratings for each km² of Germany [52] and the population data [77] were
 335 collected for a total of 357,588 viewpoints representing the centroids of each km² in
 336 Germany.

337 For the parameters used in this analysis, we set the observer height to 1.8 m, to
 338 reflect the upper bound of eye-level height of people in Germany, according to human

339 body dimensions data for ergonomics standard [78]. This is to account for areas with
340 bare-earth elevation height. We set a utility-scale wind turbine hub height (target
341 height) of 130 m, based on an expert survey [79] of expected wind turbine hub height
342 in 2035. The hub height is employed as the target height instead of total height to
343 prevent overestimation of visibility, due to different angle of views of the observer [55]
344 and visibility at night time that depends on lights placed on top of the turbine hub.
345 For the solar PV height, we used a height of 2 m to also account for agri-PV. The
346 most common visibility threshold for wind turbine viewshed analyses is 10 km [28], as
347 the visual impact of wind turbines on scenic landscapes is said to be negligible beyond
348 this distance [55]. In the present article, we used a visibility threshold of 11 km, which
349 accounts for the additional distance to the viewpoint in the center of each km² in the
350 grid. For solar PV, the visibility threshold is 6.5 km [80]. Using the same consideration
351 as for wind turbines, we set the visibility threshold to 7.5 km for the reverse viewshed
352 analysis. Additional considerations such as earth curvature and atmospheric refraction
353 were neglected, as these factors would not contribute significantly to the final results,
354 but would require significantly more computational power.

355 Due to the large number of viewpoints analyzed in this study, which requires
356 considerable computational power, the calculation of reverse viewsheds was performed
357 on a high-performance computer cluster. The analysis was performed in parallel on
358 several computing nodes for each county in Germany using GRASS-GIS version 7.8
359 [75]. This software was chosen because it is open-source, relatively lightweight, and its
360 functions can be accessed without explicitly starting the program, making it easy to
361 use in scripts and batch processes.

362 After generating individual viewsheds for each km² grid cell in Germany, the view-
363 sheds of viewpoints that meet the scenicness rating or population density thresholds
364 of each scenario (scenicness = 9, ≥ 8 , ≥ 7 , ≥ 6 , ≥ 5 , or population density \geq
365 5000 people/km², ≥ 3500 people/km², ≥ 1500 people/km², ≥ 300 people/km²) were
366 merged using the r.series function in GRASS-GIS. The merged R-ZTV maps from each
367 scenario were used as exclusion zones in the land eligibility and potential analyses.

368 Land eligibility and renewable energy potential assessment

369 The merged R-ZTV maps for different visibility scenarios were incorporated into a
370 land eligibility assessment as an additional exclusion zone. The open-source framework
371 ETHOS.GLAES [71, 72], which is based on the Geospatial Data Abstraction Library
372 (GDAL)[81] was employed for this assessment. ETHOS.GLAES allows binary land
373 exclusions based on user-defined criteria over the study region. The base scenario
374 employs multiple high-resolution land exclusion maps (see Supplementary Table 1)
375 from potential analysis conducted by Risch and Maier et al. [54]. Fig. 1b. in the main
376 article illustrates the integration of reverse viewshed maps (R-ZTV maps), combined
377 with other land exclusion datasets in the land eligibility assessment for onshore wind
378 in Aachen, Germany.

379 The base scenario for onshore wind includes forest and protected landscapes as
380 eligible areas [54]. The ETHOS.GLAES algorithm subsequently places onshore wind
381 turbines on the remaining eligible area while maintaining a spacing distance between
382 turbines of eight times the rotor diameter parallel to the main wind direction and

383 four times the rotor diameter perpendicular to it [54, 72]. A reference onshore wind
384 turbine size of 130 m hub height, 174 m rotor diameter, and 5.5 MW capacity was
385 assumed [79]. However, as the average wind speed at each federal state varies across
386 Germany, different wind turbine sizes were utilized for each federal state, reflecting
387 the optimal size [72]. Electricity generation simulations were then conducted using
388 ETHOS.RESKit [72], employing the ERA5 reanalysis data, with an assumed 15% loss
389 factor to account for losses due to wake effects [82].

390 The base scenario for offshore wind turbines excludes military areas and has a
391 15 km buffer distance from the coastline. Future offshore wind turbine designs with
392 a capacity of 17 MW, a hub height of 151 m, and a rotor diameter of 250 m was
393 utilized [79]. The same rotor diameter distances were maintained between turbines as
394 for onshore wind, and a 15 % loss factor was assumed.

395 Finally, to derive the eligible area for placing open-field PV in the base scenario, we
396 combined areas with low soil quality and 500 m long shoulder strips of motorways and
397 railways in accordance with the subsidy areas of the latest Renewable Energy Sources
398 Act [56]. A capacity density of 79.2 MW/km² was assumed [54]. ETHOS.RESKit was
399 also utilized to simulate the electricity supply of solar PV at the eligible sites for each
400 visibility scenario utilizing the ERA5 reanalysis data.

401 Energy system optimization

402 The ETHOS.NESTOR energy system model [83] serves as one of the foundations for
403 the present analyses. This optimization model is based on the ETHOS.Fine model-
404 ing framework [73, 74] and maps the national energy supply from primary energy to
405 final energy across all potential paths and technologies. The objective function is to
406 minimize the total system costs. Taking into account externally specified boundary
407 conditions (e.g., greenhouse gas reduction targets) and assumptions (e.g., industrial
408 goods production, transport demand), the most cost-effective combination of tech-
409 nologies and energy sources is determined. In order to determine the transformation
410 pathways, the cost-optimized hourly-resolved operating plans were used. This result
411 can be interpreted as the decision of a "central" planner and represents an economically
412 overarching perspective.

413 A distinctive feature of the model is that all potential GHG-reduction options
414 across all sectors (i.e., energy, transport, buildings, industry) are integral in compe-
415 tition with each other. One of the most important boundary conditions of this study
416 are the exogenously overarching greenhouse gas reduction targets set by the current
417 Climate Change Act. This target path must be adhered to by the model in any case.
418 The technologies and sectoral reduction contributions that can be utilized to achieve
419 this target path are the result of the cost optimization calculation. This means that
420 important energy consumption, such as electricity consumption or hydrogen demand,
421 are not exogenously assumed and predetermined, as is often the case in many other
422 studies. Instead, it results from the diverse cost-optimized combination of different
423 technologies and their use.

424 In the case of hydrogen, for example, this means that no specific hydrogen demand
425 is assumed for individual years, but that specific energy services are extrapolated into
426 the future (e.g., the amount of steel produced in Germany or the tonne-kilometres

427 travelled by trucks in Germany). These services can be provided via different routes
428 within the model (e.g., crude steel production via the coke-fired blast furnace or with
429 hydrogen in direct reduction plants, or the use of diesel trucks compared to fuel cell
430 trucks). The model selects the option that can fulfill the respective service in the most
431 cost-effective manner and meet all externally set constraints (e.g., greenhouse gas
432 reduction targets). The model does not consider cost-effectiveness on a sectoral basis;
433 rather, it assesses the cost-effectiveness of the entire system. This not only guarantees
434 a cost-optimal solution at the system level, but also makes it possible to analyze the
435 system benefits of the various solutions. In the case of hydrogen, the possibility of
436 long-term seasonal storage should be mentioned here in particular, which makes it
437 possible to operate the energy system robustly even during cold dark doldrums. The
438 requisite scale of hydrogen storage facilities and the proportion of renewable electricity
439 to be converted into hydrogen for optimal operation of renewable energy plants can be
440 assessed by the integrated energy system model ETHOS.NESTOR, which optimizes
441 the use of hydrogen model-endogenously.

442 The model results must not be interpreted in the sense of an expectation and
443 therefore do not represent forecasts. Rather, scenarios should be understood in the
444 sense of "what if...". The aim of the model calculations is to identify robust, cost-
445 optimal paths and trends that are independent of today's tax and subsidy mechanisms
446 that provide a sound basis for decision-makers in politics and business. The model has
447 been described, used, and extended in numerous studies, including Refs. [83–85].

448 Limitations

449 While this study has expanded upon earlier works [41, 48] by incorporating visual
450 impact considerations into techno-economic analysis and at a substantially larger plan-
451 ning scale, a number of limitations should be acknowledged. Firstly, a nationwide
452 scenicness dataset utilized to generate reverse viewshed maps is currently only avail-
453 able for Germany and Great Britain. To enable similar assessments in other regions,
454 proxies of landscape importance or scenicness would be required. This could be loca-
455 tions of national parks, heritage sites, or other designated important landscapes [51].
456 However, even such datasets may not be available for every country [48]. Alternatively,
457 future studies could use public-selected landscapes of importance or to characterize
458 areas where opposition due to landscape impacts has been documented in the past.
459 Secondly, the scenicness dataset employed has a relatively low resolution of 1 km².
460 This may result in the omission of heterogeneity in landscape quality within a 1 km²
461 area. Nevertheless, the impact on the resulting reverse viewshed map is anticipated
462 to be minimal, given the relatively larger visibility thresholds assumed compared to
463 scenicness dataset resolution (i.e., 11 km for wind turbines and 7.5 km for open-field
464 PV). Thirdly, the input of the reverse viewshed analysis employed in this study is a
465 digital surface model (DSM), which captures both natural and artificial features, e.g.,
466 buildings and trees. At locations with a high number of features such as forests and
467 cities, the reverse viewshed obtained might be overestimated since the observer point
468 is assumed to be on top of these features. However, due to the large geographic scale of
469 this study, the deviation is negligible. A sensitivity analysis (see Supplementary Fig.
470 16) indicates that the calculated eligible area exhibits minimal variation (0 – 0.5%)

471 when either digital surface model (DSM) or digital terrain model (DTM) is employed
472 in the reverse viewshed calculation. A detailed viewshed analysis with much higher
473 spatial resolution could combine the DSM with a digital terrain model (DTM), which
474 is a bare-earth elevation model, to detect possible features blocking the line of sight.
475 This improvement could be beneficial for a micro-level (i.e., municipal) analysis where
476 exact locations of power plants need to be determined. This approach is, however,
477 constrained by the the current availability of DTM data, which is only accessible for
478 selected regions. Additionally, a uniform 130 m turbine hub height was assumed in the
479 reverse viewshed calculation, despite the use of varying optimal wind turbine heights
480 (i.e., hub height of 130 – 170 m) for each federal state in the potential analysis. Nev-
481 ertheless, the variation in the resulting eligible area remains minimal of 0 – 0.2% (see
482 Supplementary Fig. 17). Finally, in our analysis we did not consider visual impacts
483 caused by grid construction. Greater electricity grid expansions may also give rise to
484 local opposition due to severe visual impacts on the landscape [86]. Future studies
485 might employ a spatially explicit optimization model to simultaneously exclude cable
486 routing with high visual impacts.

487 Data availability

488 All frameworks used for this study are open-source. The developed code for
489 the large-scale reverse viewshed analysis can be accessed on Jülich DATA,
490 doi:10.26165/JUELICH-DATA/PLNH9P. The software tool ETHOS.GLAES, used
491 for land eligibility analysis can be found at [https://github.com/FZJ-IEK3-](https://github.com/FZJ-IEK3-VSA/glaes)
492 [VSA/glaes](https://github.com/FZJ-IEK3-VSA/glaes). The ETHOS.Reskit tool, which is employed for the electricity genera-
493 tion simulation can be be accessed via <https://github.com/FZJ-IEK3-VSA/RESKit>.
494 Finally, the ETHOS.Fine energy system optimization framework can be found at
495 <https://github.com/FZJ-IEK3-VSA/FINE>.

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779 **Competing interests**

780 The authors declare no competing interests.

781 **Additional information**

782 **Supplementary information** containing Supplementary Table 1 and Supplementary
783 Figures 1 – 17 are available for this paper on a separate file.

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